

**BRIGHT
SPACE**

**Designing a Roadmap for
effective and sustainable strategies
for assessing and addressing
the challenges of EU agriculture
to navigate within
a Safe and Just Operating Space**

**Funded by
the European Union**

Increasing the contribution of EU agriculture to climate change action

The European Green Deal, aims, among others, to increase the contribution of EU agriculture to climate change action, improve the management of natural resources, ensure a fair economic return for farmers, and reinforce the protection of biodiversity. EU agriculture and food practices are currently not on the right track to meet the Green Deal ambitions and objectives. These objectives are interdependent, and while often aligned, they may also compete.

Project structure

Effective and sustainable strategies to navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space

Synergies and trade-offs between socio-economic and environmental outcomes are brought together in the concept of a Safe and Just Operating Space, where the Safe component reflects the bio-physical boundaries of the ecosystem and the Just component the requirements for the well-being of the involved people.

The BrightSpace collaboration responds to this challenge by designing effective and sustainable strategies to navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space. BrightSpace provides an analytical toolbox to experiment, analyse, and coordinate the effects of innovative technologies, governance structures, as well as short- and long-term policies related to agriculture, thereby allowing for the execution of consistent, coherent, and lasting strategies with the desired consequences.

Specific objectives

- To define, operationalise and better understand the DETERMINANTS and indicators that are crucial for the Safe and Just Operating Space in EU Agriculture.
- To improve the ability of decision makers to foresee and respond to FUTURE Safe and Just Operating Space.
- GUIDANCE to stakeholders which will allow them to take effective and sustainable actions.
- To create an Agricultural Safe and Just Operating Space PLATFORM for stakeholders' engagement at different stages of the project and capacity building.

Diversity of challenges, support for effective and sustainable actions

The project emphasises the diversity of challenges regarding the Safe and Just Operating Space across countries and regions and delivers new empirical evidence on cause-effect relations between drivers and outcomes relevant for the Safe and Just Operating Space.

A harmonised data framework and modelling toolbox are developed for medium-term and forward-looking projections of possible Safe and Just Operating Space futures by 2050 and beyond.

The support for effective and sustainable actions will include the identification of critical pathways for technological, institutional, and consumer-oriented options for EU policies in the areas of agriculture, climate change, trade, and energy.

BrightSpace builds on established modelling tools that are used to predict the impacts of climate, agricultural, and forestry policies, at the local, national, and regional levels.

Expected results

- Assessment of the potential of innovative policy options able to bridge the gap between targeted safe and just space, and the safe and just outcomes achieved with planned policies.
- Creating a Stakeholder Community that brings together BrightSpace experts and EU modelers and analysts providing them with an open access to the BrightSpace Integrated Modelling Toolbox via cloud-based solutions and interactive dashboards.
- Instrumental and conceptual impact on agricultural policy analysis will be fostered through a programme of active engagement with key stakeholders by project partners at regional, country and EU levels.
- BrightSpace tools and interactive dashboards will provide an assessment of the trade-offs and synergies of Sustainable Development Goals that impact or are impacted by EU agriculture.
- Transition Pathways and Roadmap in which a medium to long-term transition narratives for EU agriculture positing combinations of innovation, finance, public policy and stakeholder engagement measures tailored to the heterogeneous nature of member states' agri-food production & distribution systems will be designed.

“Identifying valid, reliable, and measurable indicators to assess the impact of policy measures and technological change in agriculture with regard to the Safe and Just operating space is a key challenge, but also a prerequisite to provide science-based information to policy makers and stakeholders.”

Marc Müller, project coordinator of the Brightspace project in Wageningen Economic Research

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